

EFFECT OF SUPPLEMENTATION OF BROWN SEAWEED (*Turbinaria conoides*) AND RED SEAWEED (*Gracilaria salicornia*) meal with probiotic (*Lactobacillus acidophilus*) ON PERFORMANCE, GUT HEALTH, NUTRIENT DIGESTIBILITY AND ECONOMICS OF BROILER CHICKENA B Palimkar¹, V K Munde², S M Wankhede³, S A Amrutkar⁴, K K Khose⁵, P M Kekan⁶,
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Abstract

An experiment carried out to evaluate growth performance, intestinal parameters, nutrient digestibility and economics of broiler production. Two hundred forty-0 day-old straight-run commercial broiler chicks (Vencobb-430) were divided into four treatment groups (L₀, L₁, L₂, and L₃). The birds in the control group (L₀) were fed the standard broiler diet as per BIS (2007). The birds in the treatment group L₁ were fed the standard broiler diet with 1 percent of brown seaweed meal (*Turbinaria conoides*) with probiotic (*Lactobacillus acidophilus*). The birds in the treatment group L₂ were fed with the standard broiler diet with 1percent of red seaweed GsM (*Gracilaria salicornia*) meal with probiotic (*Lactobacillus acidophilus*) and the birds in the treatment group L₃. were fed with the standard broiler diet with 0.5 percent brown seaweed TcM(*Turbinaria conoides*) and 0.5 percent red seaweed GsM (*Gracilaria salicornia*) meal with probiotic(*Lactobacillus acidophilus*). There was no appreciable variation in the total feed intake between the L₀ control group and the treatment groups (L₁, L₂, and L₃). The total body weight gain was statistically not significant in all groups but there was numerically significant value in all treatment groups (L₁, L₂, L₃) than the control group(L₀), total FCR was significantly (P<0.01) differed among the groups. The villus height and depth of crypt showed non-significant results. Digestibility of all the nutrients were non-significant but CF digestibility was found to be significantly improved in all the treatment groups. The highest net profit per kg live weight was Rs 26.855 in the treatment group L₃. The combination of red seaweed meal (*Gracilaria salicornia*) and brown seaweed (*Turbinaria conoides*) with probiotic (*Lactobacillus acidophilus*) enhanced growth performance, nutrient digestibility and profitability. Additionally, boosted the lactobacillus count and decreased the E. Coli count.

Keywords: Broiler, lactobacillus acidophilus, growth performance, economics.

Introduction

India's poultry business has experienced significant expansion over the past few decades and has effectively evolved from traditional backyard farming into a thriving agri-based sector (Panda and Samal, 2016). India is currently the world's third-largest producer of eggs and sixth-largest producer of poultry meat (Singh, 2022).

Feed costs one of the highest amounts in the production of chicken. Feed makes up 75-80% of the cost of producing layers and 65-70% of the cost of producing broilers(Panda and Samal, 2016). The ongoing rise in the cost of compounded feed and poultry feed components is causing a decline in profits for poultry farms. Therefore, effective and balanced feeding is of utmost importance to the outstanding chicken germplasm for efficient chicken production. In order to increase poultry production, a number of feed additives—such as synthetic hormones and antibiotics have been widely used. However, consumers face several health hazards from these feed additives due to the rise of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains and the residue these compounds leave in meat and eggs. Numerous studies have been working to find effective nutritional supplements, such as probiotics and prebiotics, spirulina, phytobiotics, and their combination to enhance carcass weight and growth efficiency and lower the death rate, as a safer alternative to antibiotics due to this hazardous effect.

Seaweeds are rich source of prebiotics (e.g. fucoidans, agar, carrageenans etc.) Prebiotics are non-digestible food components (readily fermentable sugars) that have a positive impact on the host by selectively enhancing the activity of one or a small number of bacteria in the colon (large intestine) and so enhancing host health (Pirgozliev *et al.*, 2019). Prebiotic consumption has been associated with several beneficial outcomes, such as the growth of beneficial microorganisms, prevention of pathogen colonisation, reduction of inflammation and cancer risk, enhanced mineral absorption, and a drop in blood serum levels of triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and total cholesterol. Because of their great nutritional value, alginate oligosaccharides and neoagarooligosaccharides—two seaweed polysaccharides with prebiotic properties—are in considerable demand as organic, low-cost chicken feed additives. (Borzouie *et al.*, 2020).

Many different microbial species, including as strains of the bacteria Bacillus, Bifidobacterium, Enterococcus, E. Coli, Lactobacillus,

Lactococcus, and Streptococcus, as well as unidentified mixed cultures, can be used to make probiotics. Species of Lactobacillus and Bifidobacterium have been used most commonly in people and animals, respectively, compared to species of Bacillus, Enterococcus, and Saccharomyces yeast. However, there has been more research on feeding Lactobacillus to animals recently. (Patterson and Burkholder, 2003). Because of their abilities to improve poultry production performance, lactobacillus strains have been referred to as advantageous additions (De Cesare *et al.*, 2017).

Along with sodium alginate, fucoxanthin (Fuco), the main marine carotenoid (Car), is a crucial component for the brown seaweed industry. Anti-inflammatory effects are seen in fuco. These seaweeds' brown colour comes from the xanthophyll pigment fucoxanthin, which is more abundant than chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-c, carotene, and other xanthophylls. Brown seaweed is utilized in animal feed more frequently than other types of algae because of its larger size and simplicity of collection. The largest seaweeds are brown algae, which come in a variety of shapes and certain species that may grow up to 35-45 m in length(El-Beltagi *et al.*, 2022). Red algae, which has about 6100 species and is marine like brown seaweed, can photosynthesize in deeper water. From thin films to filamentous and membranous forms of 1 m, the size is varied. Carotene, lutein, zeaxanthin, and chlorophyll are hidden by the pigments phycoerythrin and phycocyanin, which also contribute to the colour. The primary reserves are typically floridean starch and floridoside, and cellulose carrageenans, and long-chain polysaccharide agars make up the cell walls(Corino *et al.*, 2019).

Taking into account the functional and nutritional qualities of the brown and red seaweed and the paucity of sufficient research, the current research study has been designed to assess the synbiotic effect of inclusion of brown seaweed (*Turbinaria conoides*) and red seaweed (*Gracilaria salicornia*) meal with probiotic(*Lactobacillus acidophilus*) on performance and carcass traits of broiler chicken.

Materials And Methods

One-day-old, 240 broiler chicken were grouped into four experimental groups, L₀, L₁, L₂, and L₃ each of which had four repetitions of 15 birds. The groups were created using a completely randomized method. The different treatment groups were fed as: L₀- standard broiler diet (BIS- 2007), L₁- standard broiler diet with 1percent TcM with probiotic, L₂- standard broiler diet with 1percent

GsM with probiotic and L₃ standard broiler diet with 0.5 percent TcM and 0.5 percent GsM with probiotic. Broiler chicken efficiency is determined by performance traits such as total feed intake, total body weight gain, total feed conversion ratio, nitrogen (N) retention and nutrient digestibility gut health. and associated costs with raising broilers. The following paragraphs and tables provide details on the experiment conducted during the research period.

Housing and management

The experiment was conducted in the College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences' Parbhani experimental poultry barn (longitude: 19.2608° N, latitude: 76.7748° E). All the pens, dividers, drinkers, feeders, brooder and floor were cleaned, washed, disinfected and the poultry shed was fumigated prior to the arrival of broiler chicks. Saw dust was employed as the litter material for the birds' deep litter system. All groups received the same management procedures, including feeding, watering, immunization and lighting throughout the experiment.

Each experimental chick received a one-foot square of floor area and was housed in a separate pen. Each pen was divided into four replications, each holding fifteen birds, for the treatment groups. Used an electric bulb to offer heat and light when brooding in accordance with conventional management practice. In each replication group's and treatment group's respective pen, brooding persisted until the animals were two weeks old. After the second week, all the birds had enough light at night. In the months of October and November, the experiment was carried out. The range of temperature and relative humidity during the experimental period were 18°C to 34°C and 30 to 88 percent.

Growth performance

Feed Intake

Records of feed offered and residues left over were maintained weekly. The feed consumption was calculated by subtracting weekly residue from the total weekly feed offered. Total feed consumption of particular week was calculated by adding up the weekly average feed consumption of the previous week with the feed consumption of that particular week.

Body Weight Gain

The live body weights of all birds were recorded accurately replicates wise on the electronic weighing machine at weekly interval in morning hours before feeding. From this data, the average weekly body weight and weekly weight gain per bird were calculated for the various treatment groups.

Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)

Weekly feed conversion ratio was calculated by dividing the weekly feed consumption by weekly weight gain. The total feed conversion ratio was calculated by dividing total amount of feed consumed up to the particular week by the total body weight gain recorded up to that week.

2. Gut health parameters

On day 42, two birds from each replicate (8 birds per treatment) were selected randomly and slaughtered to determine intestinal weight, intestinal length, duodenum thickness, intestinal pH and microbial count of each bird. By subsequent opening of carcasses of birds, the entire gastrointestinal tract was removed aseptically.

i) Total Viable Count (TVC)

The Total viable count (TVC) was determined by using plate count agar as per the method of ISO 4833 (2013). A quantity of 1 ml of inoculum from 10⁻⁵ and 10⁻¹⁰ dilutions was placed in sterile petri plates in duplicates. Molten plate count agar (Hi-Media Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai) (45-50°C) was poured and mixed thoroughly by rotating the plate. The plates were allowed for solidification and kept in an incubator at 37°C for 24 hrs. The Total Viable Count value was expressed as log cfu/g by using the following formula-

$$\text{Cfu/g} = \frac{\sum C}{V [n_1 + (0.1 \times n_2)] \times d}$$

Wherein,

∑C=Total number of colonies counted from all plates

V= Volume of inoculum on each petri plate in ml

n₁= No. of plates of lower dilution

n₂= No. of plates of higher dilution.

D =Dilution factor

ii) Differential count

Differential count for selected organisms were enumerated using various differential and selective media employing spread plate technique. A tenfold serial dilution of sample prepared of TVC were used. 0.1 ml inoculum from 10⁻³ and 10⁻⁴ dilution was deposited on preformed sterile solid media and inoculum was spread with sterile triangular shaped stainless-steel spreader. Plates were incubated as per the standard technique and colony forming units were counted and expressed as cfu/g for chicken carcasses.

iii) Isolation and enumeration of E. coli (ISO 16649-2:2001)

Eosin Methylene Blue agar (EMB agar) (Hi-Media Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai) was used for the isolation and identification of E. coli. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hrs. Colonies of E. coli appear greenish metallic sheen in reflected light, dark or even black centre in transmitted light.

iv) Lactobacillus count

Lactobacillus MRS agar (Hi-Media Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai) was used for the isolation and identification of lactobacillus. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hrs. Colonies of Lactobacillus appear whitish in transmitted light.

v) Histopathology of intestine

At the time of sacrifice, intestine of sacrificed birds were collected for histopathological examination. The samples were fixed in 10% formalin solution as per the scheduled time.

The fixed tissues of organs were cut into proper size of small thickness and processed routinely to obtain paraffin sections of about 3-5μ. The sections of tissues were stained by Mayers Haematoxyline and Eosin staining method (Singh and Sulochana, 1997) for histopathological studies. Stained sections were examined under microscope in Department of Veterinary Pathology, College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Parbhani, MAFSU.

3. Nutrient retention and digestibility

In order to observe nitrogen retention metabolic trial was carried out for a period of three consecutive days after the end of 6th week of age. Eight birds from each treatment group (two birds from each replicate) representing the average body weight of the group were randomly chosen and housed in metabolic cage with provision of separate feeders and drinkers. The arrangement was also made for collection of excreta using clean dry polythene sheet spread over the dropping trays and birds were offered weighed quantity of experimental ration. During the metabolic trial, the droppings of individual birds from different groups were collected daily on 24 hours interval. The excreta was made free from feathers, extraneous and then weighed. The 1/10th representative samples from each group were drawn and stored in labelled wide mouth glass bottle containing 10% H₂SO₄ for nitrogen estimation. However, remaining dried fecal sample was oven dried for other proximate analysis as per AOAC (2000).

Proximate composition of faeces

The chemical analysis of the broiler faeces was carried out as per AOAC (2000) for all the proximate principles.

4. Economics of Broiler Production

The cost of the chick, the cost of the total feed consumed by the bird, the cost of the litter, the cost of vaccinations, and the cost of medications were all factored into the calculation of the overall cost of maintaining the broiler chicks for the entire trial. The average cost of feed per chicken was estimated using the market price per kg of each feed component. The market rate for live weight of bird per kg was used to determine the gross return per chick. The net profit per kilogram of live weight of birds realised in all treatment groups relative to the control was taken into account to compute the relative economic efficiency percent, which was then reported as a percentage.

Statistical Analysis

The data collected during the experiment were subjected to statistical analyses as per Completely Randomized Design (CRD) method with treatment as factor following statistical procedure of Snedecor and Cochran (1994). Means were compared as per Duncan's multiple range test and data were processed for statistical analyses using SPSS Software package (26.0).

Results And Discussion

Total feed intake

The study's data findings, which are shown in table 1, indicate that throughout the experiment, there was no appreciable variation in the total feed intake between the L₀ control group and the treatment groups (L₁, L₂, and L₃). According to Jung et al. (2023) Prebiotics and probiotics were not shown to have a significant impact on broiler chicken feed intake. The average total feed consumption of the experimental birds obtained in this study is comparable to that of Khalilnia et al., 2023 who reported that the starter, grower and overall (days 1– 42) periods, the highest daily feed intake was obtained with treatments PRO.5SP0.2, PC (except for overall period), PR1, and SP0.2, respectively, which showed a significant difference with the COP treatment (p < 0.05). Balasubramanian et al. (2021), who discovered that the addition of red seaweed to broiler diets did not

(P>0.05) significantly affect the feed intake of chicken broilers. According to Andri et al. (2022), broiler chickens' total FI was not significantly affected (P>0.05) by dietary seaweed.

The findings of this investigation differ from those Babu et al., (2016) who found that the cumulative feed intake per chick under various treatments. During the first three weeks of life, the T₄ (synbiotic) group consumed more feed cumulatively per chick than the T₀ (control) group, and during the fourth and sixth weeks of life, the T₄ group consumed more feed than the T₃ (probiotic) group.

The findings of this investigation differ from those of Hassan et al. (2022), who discovered that birds treated with *Spirulina platensis* (SP) had a numerically lower cumulative feed intake from day 1 to day 56. In birds given meals supplemented with 1% SP, the lowest significant (P<0.05) result was observed. According to Hussein (2018), there were significant (P<0.05) differences in the total feed consumption amongst the dietary treatments containing brown algae at levels 2, 3.5, and 5 percent. Akinyemi et al. (2022) discovered that when grill chickens are fed brown seaweed as part of their diet, the total amount of feed consumed varies considerably (P<0.05) across all treatment groups.

Table 1. Growth parameters of experimental broiler chicken

Age in week	Parameters	L0	L1	L2	L3	SEM	P-value
1 st week	BWG g/bird	101.9 ^a ±1.854	107.78 ^{ab} ±1.938	102.46 ^a ±1.14	110.4 ^b ±2.4	1.25	0.020
	FI g/bird	111.5 ^a ±0.866	111.55 ^a ±0.595	111.7 ^a ±0.600	117.45 ^b ±0.710	0.726	0.001
	FCR	1.095±0.025	1.036±0.0202	1.0909±0.015	1.065±0.0249	0.011	0.247
6 th week	BWG g/bird	2333.5±19.83	2397.7±19.420	2380.06±13.36	2402.58±29.053	12.05	0.111
	FI g/bird	3522.95 ^c ±23.480	3458.08 ^b ±15.62	3471.4 ^{bc} ±17.39	3381.4 ^a ±16.97	15.499	0.001
	FCR	1.51 ^b ±0.022	1.44 ^a ±0.016	1.4465 ^a ±0.009	1.4078 ^a ±0.009	0.0118	0.004

*Means bearing different superscripts 'a' and 'b' in a row differ significantly (P<0.05)

Total body weight gain

The total body weight gain were statistically not significantly different in all groups but there was numerically increased value in all treatment groups (L₁,L₂,L₃) than the control group(L₀). The experimental birds in the L₀, L₁, L₂, and L₃ groups had final average total body weights of 2333.5, 2397.7, 2400.06and 2402.58, respectively.

In agreement to the present study Sarangi et al (2016) found that there was no significant difference in the cumulative body weight gain of broilers between different treatments from the first to the sixth week of age. It was discovered that there were no significant changes in the grill groups' cumulative body weight increase between T₃ and T₄ or between T₁, T₂, and T₃ groups. As in the first three weeks (0–3 weeks) of life, the cumulative live body weight also increased in the second three weeks (4-6 weeks).

Consistent with the current investigation, Andri et al. (2020) discovered that grill chickens' average body weight gain increased significantly (P<0.05) when fed seaweed. According to Balasubramanian et al. (2021), the total BWG of chicken broilers was considerably (P<0.05) impacted by the inclusion of red seaweed in their meals.

Contrary to the findings of the current investigation, Hassan et al. (2022) discovered that there was no significant (P>0.05) difference between the groups of grill birds fed *Spirulina platensis* (SP) and those that were not.

Total FCR

From the data shown in table no.1, it was observed that in. In 1st week, average FCR was non significantly (P<0.05) differed among the groups but it was numerically improved in all treatment groups in which L₃, followed by L₁, L₂ and L₀. In 6th week, average FCR was

significantly (P<0.01) differed among the groups

The findings of the current study are similar with the findings of Awad *et al.*, (2009) who reported that feed conversion rate were significantly (P < 0.05) increased by the dietary inclusion of the synbiotic compared with the control and probiotic-fed broilers. Also, the results of the present study are similar with the findings of the Mookiah et al., (2013) who reported that from first-to-21, 22-to-42, and 1-to-42-day FCR values of broiler chickens in the PRO, PRE05, PRE10, SYN05, and SYN10 treatments were substantially (P<0.05) better than those in the control treatment.

The results of this investigation are not consistent with those of Sarangi et al. (2016), who found no discernible differences between the probiotic, prebiotic, and control groups. Similarly, between 22 and 42 days, there was no appreciable difference in the FCR between the prebiotic and synbiotic groups and the control group. The observed results were consistent with those of Talebi et al. (2018), who demonstrated that probiotic treatment dramatically reduced feed conversion rate (FCR) in broiler chickens.

2.Gut health

Findings from the table no.2. shows that total viable count was highly significant among the group with highest count for L₁ followed by L₃, L₂ and L₀ group. Lactobacillus count was also highly significant wherein the highest count was of L₃ followed by L₁, L₂ and lastly L₀. For E. Coli Count the values were highly significant and the count was highest for L₀ then L₂, L₁ and lastly L₃. Villus height is highly significant where the count was high for L₃ followed by L₁, L₂ and L₀. For Depth of crypt values varies from L₀, L₂, L₁ and lastly L₃ in ascending order and the count was also observed as highly significant.

The findings of current study are in agreement with Choi et al (2016)

who found that the cecal Lactobacillus count was increased ($p < 0.01$) for PR (Probiotic) and EC (Ecklonia cava) while *E. coli* was decreased ($p < 0.05$) in both supplements. The population of cecal Lactobacillus count was increased in the diet added with PR and EC and the population of *E. coli* decreased ($p < 0.05$) in both supplements (Table 4). No significant interaction was found between supplemented groups. According to Khalilnia et al., (2023), combining probiotics with Spirulina Platensis powder (PR0.5SP0.3) led to a substantial decrease in the population of Escherichia coli and a significant rise in Lactobacillus bacteria when compared to PC positive control 1 (basic diet + salinomycin antibiotic) therapy ($p < 0.05$)

Balasubramanian et al., (2021) found that Dietary supplementation with seaweed led to a linear increase in Lactobacillus sp. ($p = 0.035$) counts, whereas *E. coli* ($p = 0.027$) counts were decreased on d 42. The dietary inclusion of seaweed influenced the morphology of the mucosa in the small intestine. Considering the jejunum, the average villus height and width were significantly enhanced in broilers fed seaweed-supplemented diets compared to the control broilers. The increase in the number of lactobacilli and decrease in number of *E. coli* may be due to consuming prebiotics has been linked to a number of advantageous effects, including the development of beneficial bacteria, the reduction of pathogen colonisation, (Borzouie et al., 2020).

Table 2. Gut health parameters

Parameters	Treatment				SEM	P-Value
	L0	L1	L2	L3		
Total Viable Count	18.92 ^a ±0.338	20.18 ^b ±0.127	20.12 ^b ±0.102	20.14 ^b ±0.112	0.162	0.001
Lactobacillus count	6.99 ^a ±0.054	7.67 ^{bc} ±0.072	7.41 ^b ±0.15	7.74 ^c ±0.051	0.087	0.001
E. Coli count	5.54 ^b ±0.048	4.905 ^a ±0.114	4.95 ^a ±0.115	4.82 ^a ±0.046	0.084	0.001
Villus height(µm)	606 ^a ±4.69	772.1 ^b ±9.62	766.5 ^b ±5.38	782.23 ^b ±6.32	19.039	0.001
Depth of crypt(µm)	88.25 ^a ±0.602	121.5 ^b ±1.25	119.8 ^b ±2.1	127.3 ^c ±1.84	3.99	0.001

3. Nutrient retention and digestibility

The average daily DMI (g/d) was statistically different ($P < 0.05$) in the experimental groups, whereas dry matter retention (g/d) and dry matter retention percent were not statistically different ($P > 0.05$) but numerically more in the treatment groups than the control group, according to the data observations shown in table 3. The experimental groups differed statistically significantly ($P < 0.05$) in terms of average daily nitrogen intake (g/d), nitrogen retention (g/d) and increased average daily nitrogen retention percent compared to control group (L₀). Average daily organic matter intake differed significantly ($P < 0.05$), organic matter retention (g/d) and percentage of average daily OM retention were not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) in experimental groups but showed numerical difference in all treatment groups than the control group (L₀). Average daily EE intake, ether extract retention (g/d) and percent digestibility of EE were statistically increased in all treatment groups as compared to control group. Average daily CF intake, digestible CF (g/d) and digestible CF percent, were statistically differed ($P < 0.05$) in all treatment groups as

compared to control group. The average daily NFE intake (g/d), average daily digestible NFE (g/d) and percent digestibility of NFE intake were statistically different ($P < 0.05$) in all treatment groups as compared to control group. The present study's data on digestibility and nutrient retention support the findings of El-Waziry et al. (2015), who showed that adding dietary seaweed to sheep's diet did not significantly ($P > 0.05$) alter the amount of dry matter consumed by the experimental groups. As shown on days 14 and 28, Balasubramanian et al.'s (2021) research demonstrated that seaweed supplementation had no effect on dry matter digestibility.

The findings of the current study were similar to that of Choi et al. (2016), who found that CP digestibility increased ($p < 0.05$) in PR (probiotic) and EC (Ecklonia cava) fed in weaning pigs at phase II (day 14-28). The findings of the current study were not similar to that of Nhlane et al. (2020), who found that addition of BSM (brown seaweed meal) did not significantly affect the values of digestibility of CP, CF and similar in case of DM and OM.

Table no. 3. Nutrient metabolizability and N retention

Parameters	Treatment				SEM	P-Value
	L0	L1	L2	L3		
Metabolic body size	1.849±0.01	1.864±0.018	1.8701±0.017	1.88±0.017	0.007	0.62
Average DMI g/d/b	135.4 ^b ±1.37	138.5 ^b ±2.89	127.5 ^a ±1.94	140.6 ^b ±3.5	1.721	0.02
DDM Retention g/d/b	84.82±1.69	87.65±2.849	80.31±1.644	91.68±3.71	1.586	0.06
DM retention%	62.55±0.58	63.06±0.97	62.91±0.389	65.17±1.00	0.438	0.13
CP intake g/d/b	26.87 ^{ab} ±0.27	27.32 ^b ±0.57	25.43 ^a ±0.39	28.0 ^b ±0.67	0.333	0.02
N intake g/d/b	4.29 ^{ab} ±0.043	4.37 ^b ±0.091	4.07 ^a ±0.061	4.48 ^b ±0.11	0.053	0.02
N retention g/d/b	3.321 ^{ab} ±0.060	3.612 ^b ±0.061	3.205 ^a ±0.153	3.641 ^b ±0.122	0.067	0.03
N retention %	77.30±1.796	82.65±0.777	78.67±2.812	81.23±1.64	1.007	0.24
OM intake g/d/b	126.9 ^b ±1.286	126.8 ^b ±2.65	115.2 ^a ±1.75	125.34 ^b ±3.13	1.635	0.01
OMI retention g/d/b	79.54±1.583	80.74±2.55	72.44±1.54	81.43±3.29	1.401	0.07
OMI Retention %	62.62±0.616	63.59±0.87	62.87±0.444	64.88±0.994	0.409	0.21
EE intake g/d/b	6.501 ^a ±0.066	8.24 ^c ±0.172	7.73 ^b ±0.117	8.606 ^c ±0.214	0.216	0.001
EE retention g/d/b	4.757 ^a ±0.09	6.389 ^{bc} ±0.206	6.112 ^b ±0.137	6.761 ^c ±0.252	0.2116	0.001
EE Retention %	73.17 ^a ±0.813	77.46 ^b ±1.153	79.05 ^b ±0.625	78.51 ^b ±1.487	0.765	0.01
CF Intake g/d/b	5.201 ^a ±0.052	5.57 ^b ±0.116	6.352 ^c ±0.096	6.159 ^c ±0.153	0.128	0.001
CF retention g/d/b	2.194 ^a ±0.0364	2.878 ^{bc} ±0.070	3.169 ^c ±0.369	2.444 ^{ab} ±0.125	0.132	0.02
CF Retention %	42.22 ^{ab} ±0.990	51.71 ^c ±1.217	49.81 ^{bc} ±5.47	39.62 ^a ±1.28	1.844	0.04
NFE Intake g/d/b	88.09 ^b ±0.89	90.53 ^b ±1.89	81.02 ^a ±1.232	87.71 ^b ±2.19	1.168	0.01
NFE retention g/d/b	54.15 ^{ab} ±1.23	57.68 ^b ±1.898	50.85 ^a ±0.925	57.91 ^b ±2.34	1.063	0.04
NFE Retention %	61.45 ^a ±0.767	63.67 ^{ab} ±0.863	62.76 ^a ±0.240	65.95 ^b ±0.987	0.545	0.01
	**Means bearing different superscripts 'a' and 'b' in a row differ significantly ($P < 0.01$)					
	*Means bearing different superscripts 'a' and 'b' in a row differ significantly ($P < 0.05$)					

Cost economics of broiler chicken

The cost of consumed feed, day-old chicks, medications, vaccinations, probiotics (*Lactobacillus acidophilus*), red seaweed (*Gracilaria salicornia*), brown seaweed (*Turbinaria conoides*), meal, and other miscellaneous expenses are all taken into account when determining the cost of production.

The price of a day-old chick was Rs 35 per bird, with feed costing Rs. 40.5, 40.5, 40.5, 40.5 per kg for groups L₀, L₁, L₂, and L₃ respectively. The brown seaweed TcM(*Turbinaria conoides*) meal and red seaweed (*Gracilaria salicornia*) meal added in the formulated feed of treatment groups was obtained from Aquagri Processing PVT.LTD, Manamadurai, Tamil Nadu, at free of cost, but market cost of brown seaweed TcM(*Turbinaria conoides*) and red seaweed (*Gracilaria salicornia*) Rs. 60/kg has been considered while estimating cost of formulated feed. So that the total costs of formulated feed were Rs. 40.5, 41.14, 41.14, 41.14 per kg for groups L₀, L₁, L₂, and L₃, respectively. The average amount of feed consumed per bird in the L₀, L₁, L₂, and L₃ groups was 4179g, followed by 4142g, 4153g, 4144g, respectively. Treatment L₃ had the highest feed consumption per bird, followed by L₂, L₁, and L₀, the control group. The L₃ treatment group had a greater average live body

weight than the L₁, L₂ and L₀ groups. At the conclusion of the sixth week, the average total body weights for the L₀, L₁, L₂, L₃, groups were, respectively, 2360g, 2397g, 2400g and 2402g.

The total cost of feed consumed was almost similar (Rs.170.400 to 170.500) in all treatment groups and that was slight less in control group (Rs.169.249). The cost of feed consumed per kg live weight gain for control group L₀ was higher followed by L₂,L₁ and then L₃. The net profit per bird was higher in L₃ treatment groups then followed by L₁, L₂ and lowest in control group L₀. The net profit per bird was Rs. 53.992, 60.835, 60.604 and 64.508 for the experimental groups L₀, L₁, L₂, L₃, respectively. The L₀ control group had the lowest net profit per kilogramme of live weight of chicken, while the L₃ treatment group had the highest. L₁, L₂, were the next highest. For the L₀, L₁, L₂, L₃ groups, the net profit per kg live weight was Rs 23.14, 25.37, 25.25, and 26.85, in that order.

Group L₃, which received a brown and red seaweed (*Gracilaria salicornia*) with probiotic (*Lactobacillus acidophilus*) meal supplement, outperformed all other treatment groups in terms of economic efficacy.

Table 4. Cost economics of broiler chicken

Sr. No	Particulars	L ₀	L ₁	L ₂	L ₃
1	Cost of day-old chick (Rs.)	35	35	35	35
2	Cost of feed (Rs/Kg)	40.5	40.5	40.5	40.5
3	Cost of (<i>Turbinaria conoides</i>) brown seaweed meal (Rs/Kg of feed)	0	0.6	0	0.3
4	Cost of (<i>Gracilaria salicornia</i>) Red seaweed meal (Rs/Kg of feed)	0	0	0.6	0.3
5	Cost of probiotic (<i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i>)	0	0.04	0.04	0.04
6	Total cost of feed (Rs/Kg) (sr.no.2+3+4+5)	40.5	41.14	41.14	41.14
7	Average total feed consumed Kg per bird	3.522	3.458	3.471	3.381
8	Cost of feed consumed per bird (Rs) (Sr. no.6*7)	142.64	142.262	142.79	139.09
9	Average live body weight at the end of 6 th week (Kg)	2.33	2.397	2.40	2.402
10	Feed consumption per Kg live weight gain (Kg) Sr.no.(7/9)	1.509	1.442	1.4462	1.407
11	Cost of feed per Kg live weight gain (Rs) 8/9	61.14	59.35	59.498	57.907
12	Miscellaneous (vaccines, medicines and litter material) cost Per bird (Rs)	4	4	4	4
13	Total cost of production (Rs) 1+8+12	181.64	181.26	181.79	178.09
14	Average price realized @ Rs. 101 per Kg live weight (9*101)	235.63	242.09	242.4	242.60
15	Net profit per bird (Rs) (Sr. no. 14-13)	53.99	60.835	60.604	64.508
16	Net profit per Kg live weight of birds (Rs.) 15/9	23.14	25.38	25.25	26.855
17	Economic efficiency EE%(15/13)*100	29.72	33.546	33.336	36.22
18	Net additional profit than control (Rs./kg)	0	3.826	3.6116	6.50

Chicks that received 1 ml of brown algae extract per litter of fresh water had the highest relative economic efficiency value (136.90%), compared to 100% in the non-supplemented chicks, according to El-naga and Megahed (2018). The recent study on the economics of producing broilers is supported by these findings. The production cost for the T4 (1% *Spirulina platensis*) treatment was higher than it was for the control treatment when SP (*Spirulina platensis*) was added to the ration at a higher cost, as noted by Hassan et al. (2022). T4 yielded the highest gross return, with T3 (0.5% *Spirulina platensis*) and T2 (0.25% *Spirulina platensis*) following closely after. The lowest gross return was observed in diets lacking Seaweed. The present results are in a similar spirit.

Conclusion

Combination of Brown seaweed (*turbinaria Conoides*) meal and Red seaweed meal (*Gracilaria salicornia*) each @ 0.5kg/100kg of feed with probiotic (*Lactobacillus acidophilus*) improved body weight gain, final body weight, and FCR also enhanced gut health and showed better margin of profit. Brown Seaweed meal (*Turbinaria Conoides*) at the level 1kg/100kg with probiotic(*Lactobacillus*

acidophilus) group showed highest percentage of nitrogen retention and highest CF retention. Combination of Brown and red seaweed (*Gracilaria salicornia*) with probiotic (*Lactobacillus acidophilus*) meal supplement, outperformed all other treatment groups in terms of economic efficacy. **Acknowledgement**

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